

THE BRITISH COUNCIL

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Andrew Williamson Esq
15 St John's Street
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your ref

our ref

15 March 1972

Dear Mr Williamson

Thank you for your letter of 13 February which as you see has taken some time to reach me, since it was posted only a few days before I was transferred from Dubai to Muscat. I am sorry for this unfortunate delay.

As far as I can remember (the relevant files are of course in Dubai) I discussed your letter of 27 December with John Derby, the Dubai Municipal Engineer, who is responsible for the Museum to the Municipality. I am not sure whether I also gave him a copy, but I think not. Your proposals were then explained to Mr Kamal Hamza, the Director of the Municipality, and we were still waiting for a decision to be taken when I left Dubai.

I think the best thing I can do is to send your February letter, with a copy of this one, to John Derby, who will now, I imagine, be dealing with all Museum business. He may already have written to you, and if not I am sure will do so as soon as he can, since a decision on your proposals is bound to have been made by now.

Yours sincerely

David Phillips

David Phillips

cc John Derby
The Municipality
DUBAI